

Recommended citation: Schmidt, K., Afonso, A., Sampaio, J., Mulet, E., & Kalleitner-Huber, M. (2019). KATCH UP! Integrating circular economy in engineering education through playing a board game. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 2096-2098). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14657458.

KATCH UP! INTEGRATING CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION THROUGH PLAYING A BOARD GAME

K. Schmidt

Aalborg University, Denmark

A. Afonso

University of Aveiro

J. Sampaio

University of Aveiro

E. Mulet

University Jaume I.

M. Kalleitner-Huber

Austrian Institute of Ecology

Topics: New Notions of Interdisciplinarity in Engineering Education, Sustainability reflecting the complexity of modern society

Keywords: Circular economy, sustainability, Game-based learning, Problem Based Learning

The last 40 years' linear take-make-consume-dispose economic model creates fundamental challenges. The linear model is based on the assumption that natural resources are available, abundant, easy to source and cheap to dispose of, but it is not sustainable, and in some cases exceeding planetary boundaries. We need a fundamental transition into a more sustainable production and consumption system. In a circular model, waste and pollution are designed out, products and materials are kept in use and values sustained for as long as possible – lowering the stress on natural systems. Engineers will be asked to contribute to the transition towards circular economy (CE) on e.g. company and societal levels. To do so, they will need competences in co-creating new, multidisciplinary solutions.

The European KATCH_e project (Knowledge Alliance on Product-Service Development towards Circular Economy and Sustainability in Higher Education), develops training materials on CE, including both theoretical background materials and tools for practical implementation of CE solutions in organizations. One of the tools is the KATCH UP! board game. The game stimulates and guides the players in generating ideas on finding sustainable, circular solutions to a business challenge. It runs in six steps, from the definition of challenge, considering CE design strategies and CE business strategies, through development of business and market ideas and ending with the preparation of a CE Elevator Pitch for the idea. The main strength is that it guides the players to come up with unexpected ideas using both CE design and business strategy cards.

No previous knowledge of CE is required, however, having knowledge about CE design and business strategies is preferred, as the application of the tool will be more agile, efficient and effective, leading to better defined ideas. A maximum of 25 participants at the workshop will get a short introduction to the basics of Circular Economy, and then they form groups and play the game. Players start the game by drawing a card with a product category, a business challenge and an intended target group. Or, if they prefer, they can define their own example. Next, they draw a circular design strategy card and a couple of cards explaining circular business strategies of potential relevance for the design strategy. The task is to solve the initial business challenge through applying circular design and business model strategies. Players are also asked to consider how to implement and market the new solution. As an outcome of the game, the players fill in a CE Elevator Pitch formula, highlighting the essentials of their proposals. The pitches are put on the wall for sharing among the participants, and they will be included on the KATCH_e website from where there is free access to the game – as inspiration for teachers and future users of the game.

After playing the game, the participants will be asked to discuss which competences are needed to benefit from the game, and which competences are supported through the game. Followed by a plenum discussion, this will enhance our understanding on how, and under which conditions, the game can stimulate the development of building CE related competences in product and service development. These aspects will be added to the abstract after the conference.

There are several learning outcomes of playing the game. One is getting a systematic approach to reflecting on how to develop sustainable and circular solutions to business and market challenges. For teachers, it helps to deepen the understanding of the type of competences needed for the transition towards CE. The game is open source and thus free to use. It can be played with students in a learning environment, at seminars with participants from different organizations, or within a single company, which makes it a very flexible tool for learning about CE. As a part of a course on circular economy for engineering students, the game invites for applying the knowledge from the course, and the outcomes can serve as a background for preparing essays, exams, etc.

Engineers have an important role in the transition towards a more sustainable and circular societal model. However, even if technical skills and competences are very important, they cannot stand alone, and they should be combined with other competences to deliver the multidisciplinary solutions that are needed. Playing the game is a collaborative exercise through which engineering students can develop their understanding of the different types of knowledge and competences needed, and how they could be combined. And gaming as a way of learning through applying knowledge is known for its ability to stimulate students' motivation and engagement.

In a class of students with more advanced knowledge on CE and/or on business perspectives, the teacher may ask the students to create relevant business challenge cards to include in the first step of the game. Or ask them to create cards with additional

challenges that players will have to also consider while playing. In this way, students may be invited to not only develop solutions, but also to define relevant problems, which are central in a Problem Based Learning strategy.